

Correction to: Deep reinforcement learning for multi-objective placement of virtual machines in cloud datacenters

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Correction to: Soft Computing

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00500-020-05462-x>

Page 2: Column 2, lines 2-4, previously read: “Specifically, we consider a decision maker that, after a proper training, is able to select the most suitable heuristic for compute the placement for each VM requested by end users.”

Should read: “Specifically, we consider a decision maker that, after a proper training, is able to select the most suitable heuristic to compute the placement for each VM requested by end users.”

Page 2: Column 2, paragraph 2, lines 4-8, previously read: To evaluate its effectiveness, a comparisons against solutions widely adopted in the literature and real-world scenarios are presented, including the use of workload traces collected in a production-quality cloud datacenter.

Should read: To evaluate its effectiveness, comparisons against solutions widely adopted in the literature and real-world scenarios are presented, including the use of workload traces collected in a production-quality cloud datacenter.

Page 4: Column 1, paragraph 2, lines 2-5, previously read: In more detail, users produce a workload composed of new VM requests, which are collected by the Admission & placement module.

Should read: In more detail, users produce a workload composed of new VM requests, which are collected by the “Admission & placement” module.

The original article has been corrected.

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